

CONSISTENCY OF COLOR MEANING IN ANTONYMS AND THEIR NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE CONTEXT OF CHINESE LANGUAGE

Saliyeva Nigora Ikromovna

“Silk Road” International University of Tourism
and Cultural Heritage s.nigora@univ-silkroad.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18677213>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th February 2026

Accepted: 16th February 2026

Online: 17th February 2026

KEYWORDS

antonym, synonym, color meaning, Chinese language, cross-linguistic differences

ABSTRACT

Characteristics of Antonyms Expressing Color Meaning Alongside its literal meaning of a concept, a word also carries a perceptual color meaning. Color meaning usually encompasses emotional, stylistic, and imagery aspects. The consistency of color meaning between the two sides of an antonymic pair can be regarded as one of the most important characteristics of antonym.

Characteristics of Antonyms Expressing Color Meaning Alongside its literal meaning of a concept, a word also carries a perceptual color meaning. Color meaning usually encompasses emotional, stylistic, and imagery aspects. The consistency of color meaning between the two sides of an antonymic pair can be regarded as one of the most important characteristics of antonyms.

The emotional consistency found in antonyms differs sharply from that of synonyms. Synonyms demonstrate their “similarity with differences,” depending on whether emotional coloring is involved. For example, in the synonym set 鼓舞 gǔwǔ (“to encourage,” “to inspire”) and 鼓动 gǔdòng (“to incite,” “to encourage”), 鼓舞 has a positive emotional connotation, whereas 鼓动 lacks emotional coloring. In such synonym groups, one word may be emotional while the other is neutral. This phenomenon does not occur in antonyms.

Let us consider stylistic coloring. The stylistic consistency of antonyms is manifested as follows: either both sides of an antonymic pair lack explicit stylistic coloring, or both possess stylistic coloring, such as one being refined and the other coarse. For example:

开 / 闭 (kāi / bì) “open” – “close”;

厚 / 薄 (hòu / báo) “thick” – “thin”;

从前 / 现在 (cóngqián / xiànzài) “formerly” – “now”;

出来 / 进去 (chūlái / jìnqù) “come out” – “go in”.

Both synonyms and antonyms in these examples lack explicit stylistic coloring and belong to common vocabulary. Examples such as 公 / 母 (gōng / mǔ) “male” – “female”, 俊 / 丑 (jùn / chǒu) “handsome” – “ugly”, 倒霉 / 走运 (dǎoméi / zǒuyùn) “unlucky” – “lucky”, 好人 / 坏蛋 (hǎorén / huàidàn) “good person” – “bad person” are widely used and stylistically neutral.

Likewise, 众 / 寡 (zhòng / guǎ) “many” – “few”, 繁密 / 稀疏 (fánmì / xīshū) “dense” – “sparse”, 美丽 / 丑陋 (měilì / chǒulòu) “beautiful” – “ugly” are refined and belong to the written style.

The consistency of style and structure in antonyms forms a clear contrast with synonyms. Synonyms often differ in stylistic coloring, reflecting subtle distinctions. For example, 吃 / 食 (chī / shí) “eat”, 好 / 美好 (hǎo / měihǎo) “good” – “fine” show that the former is stylistically neutral while the latter is characteristic of written language. Similarly, 信 / 函 (xìn / hán) “letter”, 妈妈 / 母亲 (māmā / mǔqīn) “mom” – “mother”, 脑袋 / 头部 (nǎodai / tóu bù) “head” demonstrate the distinction between spoken and written styles. In contrast, antonyms preserve stylistic and emotional symmetry, with both sides being either refined or coarse. This stylistic and color consistency is a defining feature of antonyms.

Antonyms also show consistency in imagery and structure. That is, if one word has rich imagery, the other does as well; if one lacks imagery, the other does too. For example, 公 / 私 (gōng / sī) “public” – “private”, 原因 / 结果 (yuányīn / jiéguǒ) “cause” – “result”, 正号 / 负号 (zhèng hào / fù hào) “positive sign” – “negative sign” do not possess imagery coloring.

In contrast, pairs such as 甜头 / 苦头 (tiántou / kǔtóu) “sweetness” – “bitterness”, 香花 / 毒草 (xiānghuā / dúcǎo) “fragrant flower” – “poisonous grass”, 高潮 / 低潮 (gāocháo / dīcháo) “high tide” – “low tide”, 硬骨头 / 软骨头 (yìnggǔtóu / ruǎngǔtóu) “hard bones” – “soft bones” evoke vivid imagery on both sides.

Especially, antonyms formed with similar sounds produce stronger imagery, such as 甜丝丝 / 苦叽叽 (tiánsīsī / kǔjījī) “sweet” – “bitter”, 冷冰冰 / 热呼呼 (lěngbīngbīng / rèhūhū) “cold” – “hot”, 慢吞吞 / 快当当 (màn tūntūn / kuài dāngdāng) “slow” – “fast”. These antonyms help people perceive the characteristics of objects and stimulate rich imagination.

This again distinguishes antonyms from synonyms, which express subtle differences between imagery and non-imagery words, such as 笑 / 捧腹 (xiào / pěngfù) “laugh” – “burst into laughter”, 高兴 / 雀跃 (gāoxìng / quèyuè) “happy” – “joyful”, 嫉妒 / 眼红 (jídù / yǎnhóng) “envy” – “jealous”. In these pairs, the former lacks imagery coloring, while the latter creates vivid imagery through metaphor or imitation.

In comparison with expressions such as 一有都有 (“everything exists”) and 一无都有 (“nothing exists”), the consistency of imagery coloring in antonyms is more pronounced.

In conclusion, antonyms occupy a special position within the lexical-semantic system, with their primary characteristic being the consistency of color meaning. The words in an antonymic pair correspond to each other emotionally, stylistically, and imagistically, which fundamentally distinguishes them from synonyms. Moreover, antonyms are influenced by the national and cultural context of each language. Cross-linguistic differences in semantic systems result in the incomplete equivalence of antonymic pairs. Therefore, antonyms are not universal but rather lexemes with distinct national characteristics.

References:

1. Nazarova S. Xitoy tiliga o'qitishda talabalarning chet tili leksik kompetensiyasini takomillashtirish: ped.fan.fal.dok.(PhD)...diss.avtoref. Toshkent: O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti, 2018.-55 b.
2. 陈延金. 同义词教学研究综述 Чэнь Яньцзинь. Детальный обзор преподавания синонимов [J] 北方文学 (中旬刊), 2017. — P. 196
3. 鲍克怡. 汉语同义词反义词对照词典 Бао Кэи. Сопоставительный словарь синонимов и антонимов китайского языка. 汉语大词典出版社, 1996. — P. 757
4. Хасанова, Д. Ш. (2025, January). МОДЕЛИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ГИДА-ПЕРЕВОДЧИКА: СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ И ТЕНДЕНЦИИ. In International Conference on Linguistics, Literature And Translation (London) (Vol. 11, pp. 36-39).
5. Saliyeva , N. . (2026). ZAMONAVIY XITOUY TILIDA ANTONIMLARNING SEMANTIK MUNOSABATLARI. Наука и технология в современном мире, 5(2), 41–43.
6. Khamdamova, C. "HSK tizimi orqali xitoy tili lug'at boyligini o'rgatishning samarali usullari." Til va madaniyat, №3, 2023.

